

A STUDY ON ORGANISATIONAL COMMITMENT WITH REFERENCE TO ITES INDUSTRY IN COIMBATORE CITY

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Abstract:

Organisational commitment is the level of commitment and involvement an employee has towards their organization and its values. Organisational commitment is also called work engagement or worker engagement. Organisational commitment is defined as a measurable degree of an employee's positive or negative emotional attachment to their job, colleagues and organization which profoundly influences their willingness to learn & perform at work. Thus engagement is distinctively different from satisfaction, motivation, culture, climate and opinion and very difficult to measure. Various studies have demonstrated that engagement is also linked with productivity, increasingly pointing to a high correlation with individual, group and organizational performance, customer experience and customer loyalty. The main objective is to analyse the level of Employee engagement with team work in the company. For this purpose a sample of 112 was collected and percentage analysis, multiple regression and descriptive statistics were used as tool to analyse the data and the conclusion is that employees in the company are engaged at an average level and various factors that contribute to employee engagement were found. By focusing on the recommendations given the company can increase the level of engagement which leads to the success of the ITES companies.

Key Words: Satisfaction, Productivity & Engagement

Introduction to the Concept of Study:

Organisational commitment is the extent to which an employee is committed, both emotionally and intellectually, towards the work, mission, and vision of the organization. Engagement can be seen as a heightened level of ownership where each employee wants to do whatever they can for the benefit of their internal and external customers, and for the success of the organization as a whole. Engaged organizations have strong and authentic values, with clear evidence of trust and fairness based on mutual respect, where two way promises and commitments between employers and staff – are understood, and are fulfilled. Engagement is two way: organizations must work to engage the employee, who in turn has a choice about the level of engagement to offer the employer. Each reinforces the other. Increasing organisational commitment has a positive impact on key business metrics. Organisational commitment is required in any organization because it can affect employee's attitudes, absence and turnover levels. Various studies have demonstrated that engagement is also linked with productivity, increasingly pointing to a high correlation with individual, group and organizational performance, customer experience and customer loyalty. Organizations with higher engagement levels tend to have lower employee turnover, higher productivity, higher total shareholder returns and better financial performance. It is also found that organizations with the highest percentage of engaged employees increased their operating income by 19 per cent and their earnings per share by 28 per cent year to year.

Statement of the Problem:

Organisational commitment has a positive impact on key business metrics. It is directly or indirectly linked to various business aspects such as productivity, growth in revenue, customer acquisition and loyalty, employee turnover and financial performance which provide a competitive advantage and contribute to organizational success. Organisational commitment serves both employees and their employers. Employees who are fully engaged in their work are likely to have higher morale, exhibit greater loyalty, progress in their careers, and even enjoy a more rewarding personal life. Thus the organisation should focus on increasing the level of engagement. Thus a study is performed at ITES industry in Coimbatore regarding the level of engagement, factors that discriminate engagement and its relation with various aspects of business activities.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To analyze the level of Organisational commitment in ITES industry in Coimbatore.
- ✓ To identify the key factors discriminating the level of Employee Engagement.
- ✓ To analyze the influence of demographic variable on Employee Engagement.
- ✓ To analyze the difference in the level of Organisational commitment between supervisors and workers.

Scope of the Study:

This study is undertaken at ITES industry in Coimbatore. The study is performed among the employees (both workers and supervisors). Only the demographic variables are taken into account and various psychological or work related variables are not considered.

Limitations:

- ✓ Due to time constraint the sample size considered is only 80 employees.
- ✓ Only demographic variables are considered. Various psychological and work related variables are not considered.
- ✓ Fear of expressing the true facts among the respondents may lead to misinterpretation.

Research Methodology:

Type of Study: The study assumes the nature of descriptive research. The study is descriptive as it attempts to describe the level of Organisational commitment and factors contributing to the same.

Sample Design: The sampling method used in this study is Quota sampling. The size of the sample considered for the study is 80 employees (40 supervisors and 40 workers).

Method of Data Collection: The study depends on Primary data. Questionnaire is used for the collection of data. The standard questionnaires are used. The questionnaire is divided into 3 parts. The first part consists of Demographic details, the second part consists of Organizational details which are used to find the factors discriminating the level of Engagement and third part consists of Work survey which is used to find the level of Engagement among the employees.

Tools for Analysis: The tools that are used are Percentage analysis, descriptive statistics and multiple regression.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Age:

Particulars	Frequency	Percent
20-25 year	3	2.7
26-30 year	40	35.7
31-35 year	34	30.4
Above 40	35	31.2
Total	112	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the age of the respondents 2.7% are from the age group of 20-205 years, 35.7% are from the age group of 26-30 years, 30.4% are from the age group of 31-35 years and 31.2% are from the age group of above 40 years.

Gender:

Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Male	79	70.5
Female	33	29.5
Total	112	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about gender of the respondents 70.5% are male and 29.5% are female in our survey.

Level of Acceptance towards Working Environment:

	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Level of acceptance towards materials and equipment	Strongly Agree	16	14.3
	Agree	16	14.3
	Neutral	42	37.5
	Disagree	33	29.5
	Highly Disagree	5	4.5
	Total	112	100
Level of acceptance towards expectation towards them in their job	Strongly Agree	29	25.9
	Neutral	47	42
	Disagree	26	23.2
	Highly Disagree	10	8.9
	Total	112	100
Level of acceptance towards distributing work load equally	Strongly Agree	25	22.3
	Agree	15	13.4
	Neutral	31	27.7
	Disagree	31	27.7
	Highly Disagree	10	8.9
	Total	112	100
Level of acceptance towards fully able to handle their job	Strongly Agree	27	24.1
	Agree	22	19.6

	Neutral	20	17.9
	Disagree	38	33.9
	Highly Disagree	5	4.5
	Total	112	100
Level of acceptance towards proud on working in the company	Strongly Agree	32	28.6
	Agree	31	27.7
	Neutral	39	34.8
	Disagree	9	8
	Highly Disagree	1	0.9
	Total	112	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the level of acceptance towards working environment were majority of the respondents (37.5%) are neutral with level of acceptance towards materials and equipment, majority of the respondents (42%) are neutral with Level of acceptance towards expectation towards them in their job, most of the respondents (27%) are neutral and disagree with Level of acceptance towards distributing work load equally, most of the respondents (33.9%) disagree with Level of acceptance towards fully able to handle their job, maximum of the respondents and (37.5%) are neutral with level of acceptance towards proud on working in the company.

Level of Acceptance towards Team Work:

	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Level of acceptance towards people working with each other when needed	Agree	61	54.5
	Neutral	43	38.4
	Disagree	8	7.1
	Total	112	100
Level of acceptance towards sharing ideas with co-workers	Strongly agree	16	14.3
	Agree	27	24.1
	Neutral	48	42.9
	Disagree	13	11.6
	Highly disagree	8	7.1
	Total	112	100
Level of acceptance towards performance of co workers	Strongly agree	5	4.5
	Agree	39	34.8
	Neutral	8	7.1
	Disagree	43	38.4
	Highly disagree	17	15.2
	Total	112	100
Level of acceptance towards enjoy working with co-workers.	Strongly agree	10	8.9
	Agree	55	49.1
	Neutral	39	34.8
	Disagree	8	7.1
	Total	112	100

Interpretation:

The above table shows about the level of acceptance towards team work were out of 112 respondents majority of the respondents (54.5%) agree with level of acceptance towards people working with each other when needed, majority of the respondents (42.9%) are neutral with Level of acceptance towards sharing ideas with co-workers, most of the respondents (38.4%) disagree with Level of acceptance towards performance of co workers, most of the respondents (49.1%) agree for enjoy working with co-workers.

Comparison between Age and Acceptance towards Working Environment:

Coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std.	Beta		

			Error			
1	(Constant)	3.085	0.3		10.286	0
	Level of acceptance towards materials and equipment	-0.06	0.142	-0.075	-0.425	0.672
	Level of acceptance towards expectation towards them in their job	0.016	0.083	0.023	0.191	0.849
	Level of acceptance towards distributing work load equally	-0.023	0.121	-0.033	-0.19	0.85
	Level of acceptance towards fully able to handle their job	-0.107	0.081	-0.156	-1.321	0.189
	Level of acceptance towards proud on working in the company	0.204	0.106	0.23	1.928	0.057
	Level of acceptance towards making more money out of good work	-0.052	0.104	-0.063	-0.494	0.622
a. Dependent Variable: Age						
R square		0.049				
Sig		0				

The R column represents the value of R, the multiple correlation coefficients. R can be considered to be one measure of the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable, in this age (Dependent variable). A value of 0.049 indicates a moderate level of prediction. The "R Square" column represents the R² value, from our value of 0.049 that our independent variables explain 4.9% of the variability of our dependent variable of acceptance towards working environment.

Age (Dependent variable) (Constant) 3.085 = (-0.060) Level of acceptance towards materials and equipment+ (0.016) Level of acceptance towards expectation towards them in their job+ (-0.023) Level of acceptance towards distributing work load equally + (-0.107) Level of acceptance towards fully able to handle their job+ (0.204) Level of acceptance towards proud on working in the company+ (-0.052) Level of acceptance towards making more money out of good work. Here, variables Level of acceptance towards expectation towards them in their job, Level of acceptance towards proud on working in the company are directly proportional to age.

The factors level of acceptance towards materials and equipment, level of acceptance towards distributing work load equally, level of acceptance towards fully able to handle their job, and level of acceptance towards making more money out of good work.

Descriptive Statistics towards Organisational Engagement:

The factors above average mean (2.82) is taken in to consideration for decision making process of the study. The factors are level of acceptance towards materials and equipment, level of acceptance towards expectation towards them in their job, level of acceptance towards distributing work load equally, level of acceptance towards making more money out of good work, level of acceptance towards recognition by the company, level of acceptance towards established career path at the company, handling promotions, performance of co workers, action taken, comfortness on place of work, good transportation facilities provided by the company, satisfaction with the company, importance of work culture and international opportunities, frequent salary increments, quality of life, treating all employees as equal by the senior managers, getting sufficient perks, support from their superior and concerned authority, feedback to support and encourage employee development, salaries and bonuses, right talent for its present as well as future strategies, training given to managers, developmental assignments, and providing meaningful pay differentiation to high performers.

Findings:

- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are male in our survey.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are unmarried in our survey.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents have completed their UG in our survey.
- ✓ Most of the respondents have more than 21 years of experience.
- ✓ Maximum of the respondents are earning from 10001-15000.
- ✓ Most of the respondents said that most of the respondents don't have opportunities to do the work best.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are neutral with level of acceptance towards materials and equipment, majority of the respondents.
- ✓ Majority are neutral with Level of acceptance towards expectation towards them in their job,
- ✓ Majority are neutral and disagree with Level of acceptance towards distributing work load equally.
- ✓ Majority disagree with level of acceptance towards fully able to handle their job, maximum of the respondents.
- ✓ Majority are neutral with level of acceptance towards proud on working in the company.

- ✓ Most of the respondents agree with Level of acceptance towards package offered at company.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents agree with level of acceptance towards people working with each other when needed.
- ✓ Most of the respondents are neutral with level of acceptance towards care taken by the management.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents are neutral with level of acceptance towards care by senior managers.
- ✓ Most of respondents (50%) agree towards acceptance formal succession management.
- ✓ In multiple regression analysis the factors while comparing age and acceptance towards working environment the factors Level of acceptance towards expectation towards them in their job, Level of acceptance towards proud on working in the company are directly proportional to age.
- ✓ The factor employee engagement is directly proportional to organizational culture and based on the results of Anova it shows that there is no significant relationship between factors related with employee engagement and organizational culture.

Suggestions:

The analysis of the level of engagement shows that majority of the employees in the company are engaged at an average level. This level of engagement among the employees must be increased because it has a positive impact on various business outcomes and the success of the company. This level can be increased by the contributing factors that have a positive impact on the level of engagement.

The management must focus on these key factors and improve them as it has a positive impact on the company's success.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that employees in the company are engaged at an average level and various factors that contribute to employee engagement were found. By focusing on the recommendations given the company can increase the level of engagement which leads to the success of the ITES companies.

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